

Role of Untouchability and Superstitious Beliefs in U.R. Ananthamurthy's "Bharathipura"

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 1

Month : July

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-2645

Impact Factor: 4.110

Citation:

Rukmani Viji, K., and M. Sinthiya. "Role of Untouchability and Superstitious Beliefs in U.R. Ananthamurthy's 'Bharathipura.'" *Shanlax International Journal of English*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 105–09.

DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3457023>

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Abstract

This paper deals with the major problems, which are prevailing in India for many centuries. Untouchability and Superstitious beliefs are the dominant crisis which cannot be erased from the minds of the people. The people of low caste suffer a lot by the oppression of high caste people. Untouchability and superstitious beliefs are the major themes portrayed by Ananthamurthy in his work "Bharathipura". This novel exposes the caste discrimination between the people who worship Lord Manjunatha and the people who worship Lord Bhootharya. Though Holeyaru the low caste people endure a lot, the upper class people didn't allow them to come forward. They face lots of humiliation in their life but they still strive for their existence.

People distinguish themselves under the name of God. Even the superior creator is not an exception from untouchability and superstitious beliefs. Education is the only remedy which can remove this idiotic thought from the minds of people. These are the aspects which are to be discussed further in this presentation.

Keywords: Untouchability, Superstitious beliefs, Marginalization, Self-identity, Tradition and Custom, Existence.

Author's Note

Udupi Rajagopalacharya Ananthamurthy was a contemporary writer and critic in the Kannada language. He was born on 21 December, 1932 in Thirthalali Taluk. He is considered as one of the pioneers of the Navya Movement. Ananthamurthy's works have been translated into several Indian and European languages. He is the sixth writer to be awarded with Jnanpith award for the Kannada language. In 1998, he received the Padma Bhushan Award from the Government of India. His main works include Samskara, Bhava, Bharathipura and Avasthe.

Most of Ananthamurthy's works deal with the psychological aspects of people. His writings supposedly analyse aspects ranging from challenges faced by Brahmin families of Karnataka to bureaucrats dealing with politics influencing their work.

Untouchability and Superstitious Belief

Untouchability in its literal sense is of practice of ostracising a minority group by separating them from the mainstream by social custom. Superstition is any belief or practice that is accepted to be irrational or supernatural. The word superstition was first used in English in 15th Century, designed after an earlier French superstition.

Thematic Analysis

This novel mainly reflects the theme of untouchability and how the Holeyaru, the lower caste people are treated by the people of lord Manjunatha. The novel begins with the protagonist, Jagannatha who completed his studies in England and returns to his hometown Bharathipura. The circumstances in Bharathipura remain the same, when he leaves to England for his studies. Even it is worse now. He was worried on seeing the pathetic and pitiable condition of the Holeyaru people. As Jagannatha's father was the head of Manjunatha temple, after his demise, the authority went into the hands of Seetharamiah, Jagannatha was also given the equal status as his father. The first thing, he wants to do, after visting home is to meet Sripathi Rao, his father's friend.

On his way to Sripathi Rao's house, he comes across his school. He has nostalgic on seeing the school. He remembers one particular incident which was said by Rao to him:

Once, Gandhi had visited, arrangements had been made for his stay there. But Gandhi, on reaching the town, had headed straight to the Holeyaru settlement on the outskirts. And so, even Jagannatha's father, as an elder of the town, had had to go there to be with him. Later, he had gone through the Panchakavya ,a ritual cleansing. Gandhi was the only person who had visited the town without making a visit to Manjunatha. (4)

Thus, people think that it is evil to enter into the streets of Holeyaru people. They don't even prefer to touch them. Though all human beings are created by God, the people of high class regard them as superior to all human beings.

Jagannatha being a graduate wants to change the situation prevailing in Bharathipura. But he did not have the proper guidance and support to help him. Though he belongs to upper class, his education teaches him to treat people equally. Another important threat discussed here is Superstitious belief. The Holeyaru people were denied of the rights to enter into the temple. It is a belief that if the Holeyaru enter into Manjunatha temple, they will spit blood. It was not real and it was just a rumour. As the Holeyaru people are uneducated beings, they accept and agree whatever the high class people says. They don't raise words against the high society people. It is all due to lack of education among the Holeyaru. Jagannatha says that those people live in the world of illusions:

People believe that Holeyaru will spit blood and die if ever enter the temple of Manjunatha. They are convinced that Bhootharya will hold such people by their feet and drag them around until they spew blood. Even the President of the country believes in the power of Manjunatha. Unless such faith in the power of this God is destroyed, Indians will never take responsibility for their lives: they will never learn to be accountable....(30).

The superstitious belief is prevailing all over the world. Since years passed by and as people get education, they start to ignore such beliefs. In this novel too, Jagannatha tries to educate the people of Holeyaru in order to abolish the thought from their heart and mind. Jagannatha tries to create a revolution among the people of Lord Manjunatha. He plans to bring the holeyaru into the shrine of lord Manjunatha. Throughout the novel, a silent character occurs, Margaret, the ladylove of Jagannatha. He used to write letters to her about the incident happening in Bharathipura. She advices and supports him in every way.

Dear Sir,

I have decided to lead the Harijans into the temple of Shri Manjunatha, famous all over the country, on that day, devotees from all over the country gather here in Bharathipura. There is a belief that Holeyaru who enter the temple will spew blood and die. If we can prove to them how baseless this belief is, I am very sure a different mode of thinking will dawn in the minds of these people. For this purpose, I request the support of progressively-minded people. (31)

Jagannatha was trying hard to demolish this caste discrimination and superstitious beliefs from the minds of the people. As soon as he published the news, all he got was a negative comment on his action. He was depressed at first but he did not lose faith. He was stubborn in bringing the Holeyaru into the temple. "I must take the Holeyaru into the temple. I must change the traditions of centuries with that one step" (60).

He wants to change the tradition and custom of people. He wishes them to forget their petty thoughts from their soul. He tries to bring a change in their attitude. He got an idea that he must educate the people and so he invites them into his house. Untouchability was in its high pitch and so the Harijans would not even enter into the streets where the high caste people live and if they see any people coming on in their way, they hide themselves and leave the place only after their departure. Jagannatha wants to change this. "They would come only to the edge of the front porch. Jagannatha would talk to them. He would say 'Think for yourselves, take decision and act responsibly'" (60).

He was able to say it in words but failed to put in action. When he informed about his plan to Sripathi Rao, he mocked at it. Rao says that the revolution would result in failure. But a thunderstruck arrives when Nagamani, committed suicide as she cannot bear the torture of her father-in-law. It affected him very much and he thinks that he would also commit suicide if he failed. This was a heavy blow to his heart and mind. The story moves on and Jagannatha starts to teach the Holeyaru people. He invites them to his house but it was disliked by Chikki. She did not like them to be in her house as they were Holeyaru and she thought that the purity in her house was polluted by them. Jagannatha says that it is not an offense to touch them. He hates that even the high society people were ready to touch the Holeyaru but the Holeyaru people hesitates and avoids to touch them because of the belief that is incorporated in their blood which cannot be changed. They feel worried for treating them as untouchables but they are the main reason to be treated like that. It is not their fault. It is their fear which makes them to act in that way. The appearance of the Holeyaru people makes us feel pity on them. "Reddish dust in their matted black hair; black blankets thrown over their bare bodies; nothing but the loincloth to cover them" (134).

To bring a change in the minds of the Holeyaru people, Jagannatha gave them each a white shirt and dhoti, so that they would also look like the people of Lord Manjunatha. Every man who wore that really felt happy. Next, he made them to touch the Saligrama, which is the precious stone of Lord Manjunatha. "This is just a stone. Touch it and see, you'll know. If you behave like this, you'll remain idiots forever" (159).

He pleads them to touch but all in vain. The Holeyaru fears that if they touch that stone, something ill will happen. Though he says them it's just a stone, they think that it's something precious which is only for the people of Lord Manjunatha. Not only Jagannatha's effort will bring victory but also the Holeyaru should co-operate with him. It is also the political leaders who are responsible for the low caste people to remain submissive. If they start to support the Holeyaru people, they fear that the upper class people would not support them as they are large in number comparing to the Holeyaru community. As Jagannatha was busy with his plan of taking the Holeyaru into the temple, there came a terrific fall in his life. He received a letter from Margaret informing him that she has been married to Chandrasekhar, his one and only friend. This was a second blow to his

plan. But he did not lose heart and he comforts him by saying that if he wants to forget her, he wants to fully enroll him in his action. "If I don't take myself in hand now, all that I've worked for all these days will come to nothing. The only way forgot it is through action"(198).

Everything was on full-fledge and it is to be executed by the Holeyaru people. This is not only for the sake of their life but for the whole community all over India. It is in their hands to strive hard for their existence. They should feel that, if they fail to take a single step for their progress then there were will be a great loss not only for them but also for their upcoming generation. They should not think them as others. They should be aware of the things happening. They should come forward to question their rights to the upper caste people. "They should take responsibility for their lives. If only they could take that one step into the temple, these who have always been outcasts" (219).

The Holeyaru people are getting ready to fly into action. But the upper class people, thinks it was such a mere act, threatens the people that they will be expelled them from their work. Being afraid, the Holeyaru begs to the high class people as it was their means of their livelihood. This shows how they are subservient to the upper class people. The upper class people use Holeyaru people only for cleaning their area. They are the one who clean the area surrounded the temple, but they are denied to enter into the temple.

The New Moon day arrived and so Jagannatha along with the Holeyaru people, dressed neatly as the upper caste people, finally entered the temple. But they were afraid that something might happen to them. But Jagannatha gave them courage and he asked them to move further into temple. "It was seven when a procession of young Holeyaru, clad in white, and their leader, Jagannatha Rao, reached the chariot street to destroy the glory of Manjunatha" (249).

It was not Jagannatha's wish to destroy the glory of Manjunatha or the upper class people, but he toils for the rights of the Holeyaru people, to be given equal status. As an educated lad, his ideas were perfectly good and if every educated man is to abolish untouchability and superstitious belief, then surely there will be a great revolution in India. As soon as the Holeyaru people entered into the temple:

The devotees make way for the protestors, taking care not to touch the Holeyaru less they be prevented from pulling the chariot. The processions winds past the decorated chariot and up the steps of temple. Whispering everywhere, a village woman screams in frenzy, 'There's no way the Holeyaru can get in. Bhootharya will drag them by their legs. He'll make them spit blood. (250)

The people have strong faith in their traditional belief. They still can't accept the Holeyaru people being treated so wildly. Though Jagannatha achieves in bringing the Holeyaru people into the temple, his revolution was fruitless. He was in great shock to see that the idol of Manjunatha was missing. It was taken away by Ganesha Batta, the Purohit's son to save their honour and identity.

Manjunatha disappeared knowing the Holeyaru would be coming... people danced in exultation, believing that Bhootharya has entered Ganesha Batta and through him had transported Manjunatha to the river the previous day so that he may not be desecrated through the entry of the Holeyaru into the temple. The faith of Indian is so deep that.... (252-253)

Conclusion

Thus people believe that the upper class people always have an upper hand and the lower class people being treated submissive. Though some of the youngsters get education, they are blind to reality. It is in their hands to uplift the life of people. People should erase the thought of superior and inferior from their mind and they should have the mentality to treat them as equal. The strong belief in untouchability and superstitious belief should be removed completely from them. The

people of previous generation may still believe in it, but the educated should come forward to remove this rubbish thought. Thus Ananathamurthy, on seeing the atrocities done to the low caste people, cannot bear this situation and so he has put all his thoughts into action by words in his work “Bharathipura”.

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